

The Vacuum – 8T

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Abstract:

By analyzing the main equations of the new framework of variational manifolds, alongside of the total variations pairing, it is possible to construct an idea that is similar to the vacuum in Quantum field theory. The total variations pairing sums to zero, so the result is a set of zeros, indicate vanishing of arbitrary variations, synonymous with the vacuum.

Introduction

The 8T setting is a Lorentz manifold, $s = (M, g)$, with (3,1) signature. The manifold is the connected manifold, invoked stationary, $s = s_0 \times \mathbb{R}$. The manifold has areas of extremum curvatures that remain as they are overtime, this are yielding time invariant acceleration from them on the matrix tensor M, given by two conditions below (1). The reason for the acceleration in the 8T is that the manifold is a part of an infinite packet of universes, which interact at areas of extremum curvatures, as g is the Ricci flow, and as a result flatten each other matrix tensor causing it to accelerate in a time invariant rate, given by equations (1.2) and (1.1). By (1.2) those manifolds are topologically invariant. Flatness is an immediate result of this framework as given by the illustration below.

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \cap \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0$$

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_1} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_n} = 0 \quad (1.1)$$

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_1} \frac{\partial s_1}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_n} \frac{\partial s_n}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (1.2)$$

The manifold experience arbitrary amount of net curvature isomorphic to prime numbers or the number one. That construction yielded the primorial coupling constants series presented in equations (1.4) to (1.43) present the first and second representation. I.e. net curvature on the matric tensor and the prime critical line.

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \tag{1.4}$$

$$F_R\# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \tag{1.41}$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \tag{1.42}$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1)$$

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \rightarrow \left[2N_1 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N_2 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7 \rightarrow \left[2N_3 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 ... \tag{1.43}$$

For example, the Electromagnetic coupling term, we have proven the invariant three to be an electron by putting it in the fine structure constant formula:

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma \quad (1.44)$$

We have described the arbitrary variations of the manifold by the term on the main equation:

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} \delta g - \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} \delta g' = 0 \quad (1.46)$$

We partitioned and discretized the arbitrary variation term and derived the existence of Fermion. In particular, we have shown that it must have an even amount of elements, which differ in sign and create nine threefold combination, and no more than two distinct elements.

$$\delta g_1 + \delta g_2 \dots = \sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i \quad (1.47)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i = 0 \quad (1.48)$$

In addition, with bosons, described by the term (1.49) as they were proven discrete amount of prime curvature on the matrix tensor:

$$\sum_{i=1}^M \delta g_i > 0 \quad (1.49)$$

In the 8T, we derived the primorial by using total variations pairing, we searched for pairs that have certain features we know about fermions. In particular the total sums of the pairs had to be two and three divisible. Below marked in black are the pairings we used to derive the series.

$$\begin{aligned} &(3,3) (3,5) (3,7) (3,11), (3,13) \dots \\ &(5,3) (5,5) (5,7) (5,11) \mathbf{(5,13)} \dots \\ &(7,3) (7,5) (7,7) \mathbf{(7,11)} (7,13) \dots \\ &\dots \\ &(29,19)(29,23), (29,29), \mathbf{(29,31)} \dots \end{aligned}$$

We calculated the sums of those prime pairing using the simple formula:

$$\sum_{i=1}^{i=N} \mathcal{P}_i = S; \quad (2.14)$$

$$N = 2$$

And each of those pairs to theorized based on theorem three, have a net curvature element proportional to the average, we searched for the first two pairs, derived the third coupling term using the formula of the primorial, without the prime pairing, and concluded the idea was correct.

$$(p_1, p_2) = (5, 13) \rightarrow N_V = +1$$

$$(p_3, p_4) = (29, 31) \rightarrow N_V = +3$$

$$(p_5, p_6) = (?, ?) \rightarrow N_V = +5$$

Up until now, reader is probability familiar with every equation presented, as those are 8T fundamentals. **From here** on out, we have a completely **new paper**. The fact that those prime pairs are in agreement with the coupling magnitudes does not mean that those pairs are exclusive or special. There is no law suggesting that these are the only pairs appearing in our theory and that is a good thing. Therefore, all prime pairing are appearing but because we have the condition of (1.48) those prime pairs of variations are taken to vanish. Therefore, we can define the prime pairs that are not suitable for the coupling criteria:

$$\begin{aligned} (p_N, p_{N+K}) &= S_N \\ S_N &\not\equiv S \\ [2, 3] &| S \end{aligned} \tag{2.15}$$

Assuming we required the original condition, for the sum to be divisible by two and three. Therefore, the majority of those pairs do not answer the condition. However since the still vanish due to being an even number and using equation, each pair could be regarded as a single distinct zero. So those prime pairs vanishing are the playing the rule of the vacuum in the 8T.

$$\sum_{N=7}^{\infty} (p_N, p_{N+K}) \rightarrow \sum_{i=1}^T 0_i$$

$T \rightarrow \infty$

We started the summation as the primes indexed from one to six does answer the criteria of coupling constants, and cannot regarded as part of the vacuum. That is because they have a non-vanishing element N_V of certain kind. Those N_V elements are violations of stationarity causing fermions to cluster. The idea was presented in the canonical equations of curvature spikes, (1.8) for fermions and (1.81) for Bosons, vanishing and non-vanishing curvature spikes accordingly:

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\delta g_i} = \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial g_i} - \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \dot{g}_i} \left(\frac{d}{dt} \right) = 0 \tag{1.8}$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\delta g_i} = \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial g_i} - \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \dot{g}_i} \left(\frac{d}{dt} \right) > 0 \tag{1.81}$$

The summation of the prime pairing to zero is resulting in an infinite set of zeros. That is synonymous with the vacuum idea of quantum field theory:

$$\sum_{i=1}^T 0_i = \mathcal{V} \quad (2.16)$$

Summing up in a concise manner. The vacuum is the result of prime pairing which do not have a net variation element, as they are not sums identical to (2.15) in their divisors. Thus, they vanish into zero. The sum of all vanishing pairs yielding zeros is the vacuum of the 8T, as presented in equation (2.16). All prime pairs appear, as previously mentioned, we can pair any even number of primes, we chose $N = 2$ for simplicity sake. The idea of the vacuum in this theory is somewhat hard to grasp, as it requires knowing beforehand where those violations of stationarity will appear, which is impossible to know. What is possible to know is those violations of stationarity **has appeared**, that is simple, where there is stars and galaxies. The vacuum idea than is more appropriate to describe in terms of short to infinitesimal time intervals, it is not a continuous entity in time.

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)

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